

Paper 41

THE ROLE SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH

Akhil S. P.*, Shruthi.P. N. *, Anwitha.K. M.*

***1st year M B A , S M S M angalore**

ABSTRACT

This paper is an attempt to study the role and impact of social media on youth. The youth is the backbone of a nation and hence the need of study is an important part of their life i.e. social media it keeps them better connected and informed. The effort has been made in this paper to determine the pattern of usage to see whether they have been caught in the trap of social media addiction. The survey was conducted through the circulation of the questionnaire and managed to receive 160 responses. The findings are generalized through these samples. The paper assisted to analyze the influence of social media on youth social life and to assess the beneficial and preferred form of social media for youth. Findings reveal that the Majority of the respondents show the agreements with these influences of social media. The paper reveals that majority of the respondents were users of social Media. The common perception among the population was that the Social media had both positive and negative impact on them. The usage of social media among youth shows the raising trend

Keywords: Social Media, Youth.

INTRODUCTION

Social media is the latest form of media and having many features and characteristics. It has many facilities on the same channel such as communicating ,texting ,images sharing , audio and video sharing , fast publishing, linking with all over world, direct connecting. It is also cheapest fast access to the world so it is very important for all age of groups. Its use has been increasing day by day with high rate in all over the world. Majority of youth is shifting rapidly from electronic media such as television viewers and radio listeners to the social media among all age of group. Youth rate is very much to shifting into social media so its influences are much on youth. This craze of social media has led to a host of question regarding its impact on society, while it is agreed that the social media affects people's living styles and it is an ongoing process to identify the nature of these influence in every society and country specially on youth .this study also focused the influences of social media on youth and their life style, trends, educational and political awareness, physical activities, social life, their learning and so on.

Andres Kaplan (2010) described in his study that social media is a set of internet based application that constructs on the ideological and technological foundation of web and that permit the design and exchange of user generated content.

A systematic review was completed to gather the effects of social networking sites on teens. One would assume that these social media sites have a huge impact on our teens; because of the way they have inundated their lives to a degree that appears incomprehensible to yesterday's youth.

Evaluating the amount of research that surrounds the usage of social networking sites in the education system, it is important to determine whether or not, have these sites led to any impact on student engagement and achievement. This paper will be therefore able to review the available literature to study and present both the positive and negative impacts of online networking on the youth.

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH

Social media is like a coin with two faces in the sense it has both positive and negative impacts on the youth. Social Media occasionally seems to be just a new set of cool tools for involving young groups. Periodically it may use it this way and that's ok there are few cool new tools around but the emergence of social media potentially has a bigger impact. It impacts upon young groups who are growing up in an age where media is not about broadcast content from the TV but is about interactivity, multimedia and multi-tasking. And it impacts upon organizations who need to remain relevant to a new generation, and who find their own work and structures being changed by changing communication tools and patterns of communications. Social media impact on youth on both ends good and bad. It is one of the most influencing impact sources throughout the world including Pakistan people do have these influences of social media which has enhanced the exposure of the people and create more awareness among youth. Youth is highly involved in social media.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEMS

The study was designed to analyze the impact of social media on youth, how social media is influencing on the youth in different aspects of social life, political awareness, religious practices, educational learning, trends adopting, sports activities and so on.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. It is likely to say that Social media is creating awareness for youth in better-leaving style.
2. It is likely to say that Social media is the swift source of information and entertainment for youth's interest.
3. It is likely to say that Social media is the great facilitator for youth in the field of education.
4. It is likely to say that youth is utilizing social media in a positive way.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the influence of social media on youth social life
2. To evaluate the direction of youth to utilizing social media.
3. To assess the beneficial and preferred form of social media for youth.
4. To evaluate the attitude of youth towards social media and measure the spending time on social media.
5. To analyze the dependency of youth on social media and it's exhausting in life routine.
6. To recommend some measure for proper use of social media in right direction to inform and educate the people.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The descriptive method was used to carry this study. And survey type research was conducted, through the questionnaire public opinion and perception was discriminate about the impact of social media on youth and statements was developed related to the various aspect of youth's life and society.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Chart:1 Preferred social media website by people

Facebook	26.5
Whatsapp	64.2
Hike	5.1
Instagram	1.1
Other	1.1

INTERPRETATION: By analyzing this chart 64.2% of people says that they using whatsapp as social media website 26.5% of people using facebook as their social media. Rest of others using other social media.

Chart:2 Is social media is a boon?

Boon	30.1
Not a boon	69.9

INTERPRETATION: : By analyzing this chart, 69.9% of people says Yes that Social media are boon.30.1% of people saysNo that social media are not boon.

Less than 1hrs	56
2-4hrs	24
Below 5hrs	11.7
Above 5 hrs	8.7

INTERPRETATION: By analyzing this chart 58% of people says that they are using social media for below 5hrs and 24% people says that they are using it less than 1hrs .

Chart -4 age comparison by using Chi square table

Association between age group and usage hours

AGE GROUP	0-1	2 to 4	4 to 5	5 more	Total
20 to 29	31	83	17	13	144
30 - 40	5	0	0	0	5
41-40	0	3	0	0	3

50 above	1	0	0	0	1
TOTAL	37	86	17	13	153

$H_1 > H_0$, 25.46 > 16.919

INTERPRETATION: From the above CHISQUARE Table it shows that there is no association between age group and the total hours spent on social media sites.

Findings ,Suggestions

- Internet services should be provided with a view to gain knowledge not to mislead students
- youth spend most of their time online on social network and blogs
- Seventy percent of active online adult social networkers shop online
- Changes are taking place in organizations' internal and external use of social media
- Youth need to be taught of the danger of putting their personal information online
- Mobile is emerging as a frequent professional networking access point

Conclusion

The research deals with a survey on the usage of the social media networking in the domain of youth. The social media referencing which is used in the research tool are WhatsApp, Facebook, Skype, YouTube, Twitter and MySpace. The questionnaire consists of 18 close ended questions while two questions are opening ended. The survey was being approached by this researcher to 160 youngsters. All the participants actively respond to this questionnaire. The return average of the questionnaire was greatly high with 95 percent

The average participation of the female respondents is greater than the male respondents with 42 percent. This shows that the social media is widely used by the rural youth living in the urban population while the urban population utilized this with marginalized interests according to this sample survey. The average age groups which are being contacted by this researcher were between 20-29 years.

The majority of the respondents were students while a smaller proportion were the people belonging to different employee groups. This shows that the use of social media is widely used by all the segmented youngsters of the society

The usages of the social media are in progress since the early years of the 21st century in India. The social media is utilized by the population belonging to different age groups but the youth population is at the forefront in the social media sites in all over the world and especially in India. The old perception of the socio-political development of the society in Pakistan through traditional elites and the clan groups has significantly changed into the new phenomena of social networking and online conferencing through the social media. The social norms of the society have weakened in the age of social media format and influence from individual to collective group efforts and progression. The majority of the sampled population of this research agrees with this argument. Majority of the sampled population is agreed with this argument that the positive use of social media forms can brought socio-political awareness, enhance the different skills like increase language proficiency, develop online communication skills, create broader visionary power and connectivity. It is also useful for advertising, job hunting portals, publishing research articles and other techniques etc.

References:

- <http://www.smartinsights.com/social-media-marketing/social-media-strategy/new-global-social-media-research/?new=1/?new=1>
- [http://www.ajssh.leena-luna.co.jp/AJSSHPDFs/Vol.3\(4\)/AJSSH2014\(3.4-13\).pdf](http://www.ajssh.leena-luna.co.jp/AJSSHPDFs/Vol.3(4)/AJSSH2014(3.4-13).pdf)
- Image 1, Awesome Social Media Facts and Statistics for 2013
<<http://www.jeffbullas.com/2013/09/20/12-awesome-social-media-facts-and-statistics-for-2013/>>

- Cosmato, Donna. "Advantages and Disadvantages of Social Networking." socialnetworking.bvetoknow.com, 02 July 2013. Web. 29 July. 2013.
- "Cyber bullying." www.stopbullying.com, 08 Feb 2012. Web. 29 July. 2013.
- Docs.google.com
- En.Wikipedia.com
- www.scribd.com
- <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>
- <http://www.pewinternet.org/2015/04/09/teens-social-media-technology-2015/>
- <https://www.scribd.com/doc/63799736/Kaplan-and-Haenlein-2010-Social-Media>
- Author: Danah Boyd (2014)

Book: The Social Lives of Networked Teens

Yale University Press New Haven, CT, USA